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A COUPLED FSI FRAMEWORK USING THE MULTISCALE UNIVERSAL INTERFACE

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Abstract: A partitioned multi-physics framework is presented that is specifically designed to solve complex sloshing flows within wing-like structures. It is designed around the structural solver /textitMSC Nastran and couples this to multiple fluid solvers in a partitioned way. This allows for a choice in fluid dynamics methodology when considering sloshing problems. While commercial multi-physics frameworks do exist, most offer limited capability in terms of capturing complex and high-fidelity 3D sloshing fluid dynamics, this framework represents an approach to couple multiple industrially relevant closed-source solvers together using a high-performance and open-source code coupling library as the connective layer. A practical overview of the design, both algorithmically and in software terms, is presented, followed by a number of high-level examples of the FSI modelling capability that the framework enables.

1 INTRODUCTION

The SLOWD (Sloshing Wing Dynamics) EU H2020 funded project [1,2] has eight major work packages, this presents the fifth, which looks to bring together work done in packages three and

four (around sloshing fluid dynamics and associated structural mechanics), into a useful and industrially relevant partitioned coupled Fluid Structure Interaction (FSI) framework.

This paper describes how this has been achieved by coupling closed-source commercial software packages of industrial importance using an open-source general purpose coupling library called the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) [3,4]. The fluid solvers provided are the Volume of Fluid based Elemental [5] and Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics solver Siemens Simcenter SPH Flow [6] are then coupled directly to MSC Nastran [7] using its programmable coupling API OpenFSI [8]. Examples of modelling results achieved so far are presented and future plans for application of the framework within the context of the SLOWD project discussed.

2 COUPLED FSI FRAMEWORK

The goal of this work is to couple the MSC Nastran structural solver with multiple fluid solvers within the same design in order to produce a software framework capable of employing different fluid dynamics methods to explore problems using the most appropriate workflow. In particular, the Volume of Fluid mesh-based solver Elemental [5] and the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics particle-based solver SPH Flow [6], both are also commercial in nature. Previous work has shown that it is possible to create a suitable FSI framework by employing the OpenFSI interface provided by MSC to enable Nastran for this kind of purpose. Both commercial fluid solvers have key developers within the SLOWD consortium and present examples of best-in-class solutions in their respective fields. The use of existing and closed-source CFD solvers defines the requirement that a partitioned coupled approach is taken.

The FSI problems of the SLOWD project demand the use of high-performance computing (HPC) for at least the fluid portions of the problem domains proposed as high-fidelity sloshing simulations taken over relatively long periods of time represent a significant computational challenge regardless of the method employed. While MSC Nastran does offer HPC capability, it is not used here, where existing industrial processes are based around the assumption that it is used as a serial (non parallel) solution. However, a coupling solution that allows for the use of HPC for the fluid solvers is fundamental. Scope for extending the developed approach such that MSC Nastran can also be used in parallel exists in the future.

In order to facilitate inter-solver communication, The Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) [3,4] code coupling library is used as the underlying framework. This library is open-source and free to use and directly developed by members of the SLOWD consortium, it is designed to facilitate HPC-oriented code couplings without significant knowledge of how to organise the complex inter-solver communication patterns this demands. Of note is that the MSC OpenFSI interface facilitates the use of a commercial coupling solution developed by Fraunhofer SCAI called MpCCI [9], however the expected HPC performance of this is not entirely clear and potential for directly developing complex spatial interpolation methods may also be limited, the MUI library is designed specifically with both of those issues in mind. The MUI library is also well-suited for use when coupling methods using different discretisation approaches as is the case here due to the use of both mesh- and particle-based fluid solvers.

The final output of the SLOWD project will be a complete framework, involving the multifaceted FSI component described in detail here but also a top-level single interface to ease use in an industrial context as well as integration of a controller model designed to introduce external forcing on the structure to mimic experimental apparatus. The framework is designed for use on HPC clusters as well as individual workstations and therefore will be applicable to a

range of industrial problem-types.

2.1 The Multiscale Universal Interface Coupling Library

The open-source general code coupling library used in this work, the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) [3,4] is an open-source C++ library with wrappers written for C/Python/Fortran. Its purpose is to allow for the creation of coupled multi-physics or multi-scale simulations and is designed entirely around the Message Passing Interface (MPI) distributed computing approach. Specifically, it relies on the Multi Program Multi Data (MPMD) paradigm that is part of the MPI standard. As a coupling library, the primary purpose of MUI is to encapsulate and simplify the creation of complex inter-process MPI communicator patterns and provide the concept of a coupling interface between solutions. The library doesn't prescribe a specific coupling methodology, rather it imposes a non-blocking send, blocking receive communication model. Through this synchronised approach, combined with spatial and temporal interpolation methods, makes it possible to build different coupling algorithms using the same fundamental tool-kit.

In order to maintain the most domain-agnostic approach, unlike other coupling libraries, MUI assumes the use of a particle-based representation for data passed through the interfaces that it creates. The basic premise therefore is that a representation such as a mesh should be refined to particle-data (for example a cell or face centre) and then MUI provides a number of spatial interpolation methods to allow this data to be transferred between different domain types. In the case of coupling codes that are mismatched in temporal terms, MUI also provides the ability to apply interpolation in time. The library is designed such that introducing a new interpolation scheme is relatively simple and its open source nature makes direct dissemination of new methods trivial. In the case of spatial interpolation not being required, the library can be used purely to transfer data between discrete solvers and the computational overhead of creating particle search structures can be avoided. An overview of how MUI can be viewed in terms of coupling two solvers can be seen in Figure 1.

Within the SLOWD project MUI has been extended to support the concept of time-stamping data using both a main and sub-iteration value in order to facilitate simpler designs involving sub-iterations. Each pushed frame of data is associated with a time in the format [iteration, sub-iteration], these are collated into a single time-frame and then a single command transmits them to the receiving end of the MUI interface as a single MPI message. At the receiving end, fetch commands are then issued using equivalent time-frame identifiers, these functions block the progress of the application they are called within until the data is available.

While MSC Nastran is not used in a parallel sense within SLOWD, the use of MPI parallelised CFD solvers is necessary. The MUI library allows for computational overhead inherently introduced by communicating data between solvers to be optimised. It achieves this by reducing the numbers of MPI messages sent based on a spatial optimisation algorithm called *Smart Send*. The basic premise of this is described in Figure 2 here it is shown how an undesirable all-to-all MPI communication pattern can be reduced to a pattern where only MPI ranks in multiple parallelised solvers communicate if they need to.

2.2 Software Design

In order to design an FSI framework around MSC Nastran, it is necessary to utilise the OpenFSI interface that MSC provide for just this purpose. There are, however, a number of specific deficiencies with OpenFSI when it is to be used as part of a partitioned framework that relies

Figure 1: The design of an MUI interface, showing the concept of the Data Frame and how data is sampled spatially and temporally.

on a coupling library other than MpCCI that it has been important for the SLOWD project to overcome. Namely:

- An inability to control the time-stepping of Nastran externally.
- No possibility to incorporate a communication protocol to enable a partitioned coupled approach (in software terms) able to be used in a high-performance computing environment.

Overcoming these problems has required specific software developments, the first in the form of a new service object for direct use by MSC Nastran, this is henceforth referred to as the *Time Control* object. This was created specifically for the SLOWD project MSC/Hexagon software and provides a modification specific to the SOL400 part of Nastran allowing an external influence to directly control the size of time-step the solver takes as well as when the solution should be considered converged and stop sub-iterating. The second problem is particularly important as utilising the chosen commercial fluid solvers by embedding them directly into the OpenFSI interface in the form of a linked library, while feasible, is not a good solution for the longevity and future maintainability of the FSI framework where a truly partitioned approach is preferable. The use of a coupling library like MUI to create such a solution generates the need for use of a suitable HPC communication library such as the Message Passing Interface (MPI). As integration of MPI is not possible within OpenFSI, a proxy application, henceforth referred to as *AirbusInter-Proxy* (ABI-Proxy), has been created and acts as the central communication hub within the presented framework design.

Two different computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solutions have been selected for use within

Figure 2: Diagram showing the basic premise the MUI Smart Send algorithm. Using a simple geometric definition of a “send” and “receive” region in the applications connected together using an MUI interface, the library will automatically determine which MPI ranks need to communicate with each other.

SLOWD. These CFD solvers are characterised by fundamentally different mathematical descriptions of the Navier-Stokes equations (with the Volume of Fluid based solver Elemental being Eulerian and the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics based solver SPH Flow Lagrangian), different space discretisation (unstructured meshes and fluid particles) and different time integration schemes (semi-implicit and fully explicit). Therefore, two notably different coupling algorithms have been developed and implemented within the coupling framework in a way that presents the user with a multi-faceted approach. An overview of the framework can be seen in Figure 3.

2.3 FSI Algorithm Design

As the framework is designed to support coupling between two very different fluid solvers, one an implicit mesh-based approach and the other an explicit particle based approach, there are effectively two different coupling algorithms implemented. However, as both consider the same structural solution, overlap is able to happen in software terms with the result being an outwardly homogeneous approach for the user.

The overview description seen in Figure 3 is expanded in Figure 4 to show specific detail of the logical algorithmic flow within each solver as well as the systemic data flow using MUI to enable the partitioned coupling scheme.

Conceptually the ABI-Proxy application and MSC Nastran (including the OpenFSI and Time

Figure 3: Overview of the coupled FSI framework design, showing the ABI-Proxy as the connecting component between each solver. Instrumentation with the MUI coupling library is shown in the ABI-Proxy and two fluid solvers where it is used to transfer coupling data. Communication between the ABI-Proxy and the OpenFSI and TimeControl components of MSC Nastran is handled using low-level shared memory.

Figure 4: Detailed block diagram view of the overall coupled FSI framework. Red depicts parts of the system where data is received through an MUI interface (and therefore represent a blocking operation) while green shows where data is sent (non-blocking).

Control extension objects) can be considered as a single entity as one cannot be used within the framework without the other. While they do exist as individual applications, they share a common shared memory structure and so one cannot be launched without the other. In an HPC context this adds an extra consideration as it becomes necessary to ensure that any scheduler

provided by the HPC platform always places the two applications in the same memory space (or compute node). The fluid solvers communicate purely using MPI through the MUI library and therefore are able to be located within an HPC resource as the scheduler prefers.

2.3.1 Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

Due to its mesh-less nature, the smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) method naturally allows for the study of FSI problems involving large deformations of both the structure and the fluid without the need for any special treatment. The chosen solver for this framework, SPH Flow, handles its boundary condition in such a way that the structural mesh can directly form the boundary condition in the SPH simulation for many simulation problems, where this is not the case then the same interpolation methods as would be used between two non co-located meshes can be utilised. Treatment of solid boundary conditions is a topic still widely discussed in the SPH literature, however the Boundary Integral Method with the Cut-Face Approach (BIM-CFA) [10] is used within SPH Flow as it is both robust and provides capability to deal with complex geometries.

In order to couple SPH Flow to the Finite Element (FE) solver MSC Nastran, the Conventional Sequential Staggered (CSS) coupling scheme [11, 12] (described in Figure 5) is used, since it represents a typical approach for coupling explicit codes with implicit, as is the case in the present work. Use in the SPH/FE coupling context specific to SPH Flow is validated in the literature [13–17], where SPH Flow has been coupled with several implicit FE solvers with success.

Figure 5: Overview of the Conventional Sequential Staggered (CSS) scheme used to couple SPH Flow with MSC Nastran. In the diagram, U and V stand respectively for the displacement and velocity of the structure nodes computed by MSC Nastran, while F represent the forces computed by SPH Flow. The algorithmic stages (1-4) of the scheme are shown numerically for a single time-step, with stage 5 representing the start of the next time-step.

As shown in [13–17], there are a number of key points to consider that are essential to obtain stable and accurate results using the CSS method. Regarding accuracy of coupling in the context of FSI, it has been shown that when the forces computed by SPH Flow show an energy-preserving behavior [15], results are improved with respect to other formulations such as the one previously derived in [13].

In terms of stability of the coupling, it has been shown that the choice of the FE temporal integration scheme is crucial. While using the implicit Euler scheme can allow for the recovery of stable and accurate results [17], for higher-order schemes coefficients have to be chosen such that any high-frequency oscillations are reduced without affecting the low frequency domain, *e.g.* by choosing $\alpha \neq 0$ within the Hilber-Hughes-Taylor (HHT) scheme [13–17].

One of the strategies to ensure numerical energy conservation that is derived in [15] consists of ensuring the reciprocity of the force between the fluid and structure solvers. This was achieved by setting the force applied by the fluid on each surface panel ($k; k + 1$) as the opposite force (given by $(k; k + 1)$) on all the fluid particles in its neighbourhood, this methodology is depicted in Figure 6. The force is then transmitted to each surface panel of the FE solver, and the kinematics are returned by the FE solver at the nodes of the corresponding structural mesh.

Figure 6: Interaction between a solid face ($k, k + 1$) and the particles in its neighbourhood.

In the present work, the HHT algorithm is used but with some notable differences compared with [14–17], coupling nodes (referred to as the *wetted* nodes in Nastran nomenclature) are used in the present work, implying that MSC Nastran sends and receives both the kinematics and forces at the *wetted* nodes location. Consequently, there is a need to compute forces at these *wetted* node locations. This is achieved by first computing the force on each panel as in [14–17] and then equally distributing it across the corresponding nodes.

While the proposed solution does not present conservation issues in 2D, using the *wetted* nodes paradigm in 3D requires more advanced solutions, the use of spatial interpolation such as the Radial Basis Function (RBF) implemented in the MUI library is one approach that will be considered during future developments.

2.3.2 Volume of Fluid

For the Eulerian Volume of Fluid (VoF) [18] method the ELEMENTAL[®] code has been employed within the framework. The VoF method has a long and demonstrated history of accurate multi-phase flow modelling. The Navier-Stokes equations are solved using a semi-implicit fractional-step method, where the liquid is assumed incompressible and the gas weakly-compressible [19].

For cases proposed within the SLOWD project the solid to liquid mass ratios are less than unity. This suggests that a weak FSI coupling approach can be taken without the need for relaxation to stabilise the commonly observed *added mass* instability. This greatly increases the performance of the coupled system since no iterative procedure is required to converge each time step. A simple stepping procedure detailed in Algorithm 1 can be followed.

Algorithm 1: The coupling algorithm designed to allow Elemental to be coupled with MSC Nastran via the ABI-Proxy application.

```

1 Initialise Elemental and MSC Nastran solvers;
2 Set n=1;
3 foreach time steps n do
4   Elemental pushes  $\Delta t$ ;
5   MSC Nastran pulls  $\Delta t$ ;
6   Elemental pulls  $\mathbf{k}_m^n$  for ( $n = 1, \mathbf{k}_m = 0$ ) using MUI;
7   Elemental solves the fluid  $n = n + 1$ ;
8   Elemental pushes  $\mathbf{k}_t^{n+1}$  using MUI;
9   MSC Nastran pulls  $\mathbf{k}_t^{n+1}$  via ABI-Proxy using MUI;
10  MSC Nastran solves the solid  $n = n + 1$ ;
11  MSC Nastran pushes  $\mathbf{k}_m^{n+1}$  via ABI-Proxy using MUI;
12  Check termination status;
13 end

```

To expand on nomenclature in Algorithm 1, the solid and fluid can each be considered as a function which maps an input set of state variables to an output set of state variables. The fluid maps some input kinematics $\mathbf{k}_m = \{\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}, \ddot{\mathbf{x}}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\omega}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}\}$ to some output kinetics $\mathbf{k}_t = \{\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\tau}\}$, where the kinematics contains the linear and rotational displacements, velocities, and accelerations and the kinetics contain the the force and torque, respectively. For the above framework ELEMENTAL[®] and MSC Nastran have been coupled via a single point about which the dynamics are respectively computed and communicated.

The force, \mathbf{f} , and torque, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, exerted by the fluid on the solid are respectively computed via boundary summation of the fluid pressure and shear stress, namely

$$\mathbf{f} = \sum_{\partial\Omega} [p - \mu_i (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\partial\Omega} |\partial\Omega|, \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \sum_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{f} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\partial\Omega} |\partial\Omega|, \quad (2)$$

where $\partial\Omega$ represents the set of fluid domain boundary cell faces with boundary normal $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\partial\Omega}$. The fluid pressure and velocity are respectively denoted p and \mathbf{u} . The torque is computed about an MUI communication point \mathbf{x}_o , such that $\mathbf{r}_o = \mathbf{x}_{\partial\Omega} - \mathbf{x}_o$.

3 FSI EXAMPLES

As the presented framework has capability to use multiple fluid solvers but using the same structural solver, this section presents a number of initial validation cases for each. Future work will look to apply each method to problems within the SLOWD project, further demonstrating capability and industrial applicability.

3.1 Volume of Fluid

To ensure accuracy of the ELEMENTAL[®]-Nastran solution an easily verified spring-mass-damper case was conducted, this forms part of the overall SLOWD coupled verification and validation benchmark suite. A schematic of the setup is provided in Figure 7, as depicted, the fluid container is completely filled. This allows for it to be treated as a *static* mass and thus a standard

damped harmonic oscillator analytical solution can be applied. (Note, the full set of fluid equations is still solved.)

For a given harmonic oscillator the governing equation reads,

$$\ddot{y} + 2\zeta\omega_n\dot{y} + \omega_n^2y = 0,$$

where ζ , ω_n , and y are respectively the damping ratio, natural frequency, and displacement along the y - cardinal axis. The $(\dot{\cdot})$ and $(\ddot{\cdot})$ operators indicate the first and second derivatives with respect to time. The analytical solution for the position and velocity is given as a function of time, t , and expressed

$$y_a(t) = Ce^{-\zeta\omega_n t} \sin(\omega_d t + \psi), \quad (3)$$

and

$$\dot{y}_a(t) = C [(-\zeta\omega_n)e^{-\zeta\omega_n t} \sin(\omega_d t + \psi) + \omega_d e^{-\zeta\omega_n t} \cos(\omega_d t + \psi)] .. \quad (4)$$

In the above ω_d is the damped natural frequency and formulated $\omega_n\sqrt{1-\zeta^2}$ [20]. With a wet mass of $2.1kg$ (dry mass of $1.1kg$), a damping coefficient of $0.377N.s.m^{-1}$, a spring stiffness of $39.5N.m^{-1}$, and an initial displacement of $0.1m$, the values of C and ψ in Equations (3) and (4) are respectively computed as 0.1 and $1.55rad$. Two numerical experiments were conducted by

Figure 7: Coupled spring-mass-damper setup.

Figure 8: Evolution of the vertical displacement and velocity of a ELEMENTAL[®]-Nastran coupled analysis.

varying time step size, $\Delta t = \{0.01, 0.001\}s$. The evolution in time of the vertical displacement and velocity are illustrated in Figure 8. To assess the error quantitatively the L -norms of an absolute error function, $\varepsilon(t_i)$, formulated,

$$\varepsilon(t_i) = |y_n(t_i) - y_a(t_i)|, \quad (5)$$

were computed. In Equation (5), y_n represents the the numerical solution at time t_i . The L_2 and L_∞ norms of the error function read

$$L_2 = \frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_{t_i} \varepsilon(t_i)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad L_\infty = \max_{t_i \in t} \varepsilon(t_i).$$

The L -norms of the temporal errors, and the order of their convergence, are presented in Table 1. The results quantitatively confirm the visual convergence depicted in Figure 8. While ELEMENTAL[®] has the ability to time march with 2nd order accuracy and similar is assumed for MSC Nastran, the coupled approach is not expected to recover 2nd order temporal accuracy. This is due to the definitive approach taken by MSC Nastran being unclear, and thus giving an inability to ensure consistency in the solution. Nevertheless, this result demonstrates a stable coupling of the two solvers.

	L_2	L_∞	$\mathcal{O}(L_2), \mathcal{O}(L_\infty)$
Displacement ($\Delta t = 0.01$)	$1.01e^{-3}$	$1.50e^{-2}$	
Displacement ($\Delta t = 0.001$)	$9.51e^{-5}$	$1.35e^{-3}$	1.03, 1.03
Velocity ($\Delta t = 0.01$)	$4.18e^{-3}$	$6.02e^{-2}$	
Velocity ($\Delta t = 0.01$)	$3.82e^{-4}$	$5.52e^{-3}$	1.03, 1.04

Table 1: Convergence of the L_2 - and L_∞ - norms of the coupled spring-mass-damper.

3.2 Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

The coupling between SPH Flow and several FE solvers has been widely validated in the literature [14–17]. However, due to the differences explained in Section 2.3.1 regarding the coupling strategy used in the present work with respect to [14–17], it is important to ensure results obtained using the new implementation are stable and accurate while using MSC Nastran. To this end, two test cases are considered here.

The first case was derived in [13] and consists of a hydrostatic column of water of height $H = 2m$ and length $L = 1m$ in a tank with a deformable bottom made from a beam of dimension $[1m; 5cm]$, as depicted in Figure 9.

The case is setup as if the deformable beam and the fluid are not in contact, *i.e.* the beam is not deformed and the fluid is at rest. Suddenly, when the simulation starts, the forces computed by the fluid solver are transmitted to the structure, therefore the beam starts to oscillate in response to this loading.

This test case is particularly interesting for weakly-compressible fluid solvers (such as SPH) since in addition to the oscillations due to the first fluid loading, the beam is excited throughout the simulation by the shock wave created in response to this first loading, which is then reflected alternatively by the free-surface and the beam. This phenomena allows an in-depth study of the stability of the coupling scheme (see *e.g.* [13]).

As in [13–15], we observe that using the HHT FE temporal integration scheme with $\alpha = 0$ the solution is not stable, while using $\alpha \neq 0$ allows for recovery of stable and accurate results.

In Figures 10 and 11, the results obtained in terms of vertical force exerted by the fluid on the beam and vertical displacement of the beam midpoint are compared to results from the literature and to a static analytical solution. Of note in the presented graphs is that results of Michel [17] using HHT are obtained using a coupling between SPH Flow and an open-source structural code named Code_Aster [21] while the implicit Euler results with a coupling between SPH Flow and an FE solver developed by *Michelin*. Results obtained using the present paper are notably similar to those presented in the literature.

Figure 9: Initial case setup for a 2D hydrostatic water column resting on a flexible beam as defined by [13]

Figure 10: 2D Hydrostatic column of water on a deformable beam. Time evolution of the vertical forces exerted by the fluid on the beam.

The second case consists of a deformable beam of height $H = 0.1148\text{m}$ and made of rubber, clamped to the bottom of a tank that is partially filled with fluid and subjected to a rolling sloshing motion, for which experimental results are available [22].

Regarding the dynamics of the fluid, 3D effects are predominant for this test case [14]. Nevertheless, most of the results in the literature use a 2D approximation, the results presented here have also been obtained in 2D.

Unlike the first test case, large deformations of both the free-surface and the structure occur (see

Figure 11: 2D Hydrostatic column of water on a deformable beam. Time evolution of the vertical displacement of the center of the beam.

Figure 12), allowing for the validation of the framework for problems with high deformation.

In Figure 13, the displacement of the top part of the beam is plotted and compared to results of the literature. The numerical results of Idelsohn et al. [22] are obtained using the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) for both the fluid and solid sub-domains (see [23]), while the Paik & Carrica [24] results are obtained using a coupling between a Finite Difference (FD) method for the fluid and a FE method for the structure, including a specific treatment to deal with the non-matching grids of the fluid and structure sub-domains. The results obtained with the present implementation are in very good agreement with these reference results.

Figure 12: Rolling tank test case. Pressure field obtained at $t = 1.84s$ (left plot) and $t = 2.32s$ (right plot).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A partitioned and high-performance FSI framework designed to handle complex sloshing problems synonymous with fuel in an aircraft wing during flight conditions has been created. This is based around industrially relevant solvers in the form of MSC Nastran for structural mechanics and two fluid solvers representing both mesh- and particle-based approaches named Elemental and SPH Flow. The open source and general purpose code coupling library the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) is used to develop the inter-solver communication layer needed to

Figure 13: Rolling tank test case. Time evolution of the beam measured at its top part, obtained with the present method for two spatial resolutions, and comparison to results of the literature. The experimental results are also plotted to represent the error of 2D numerical results in comparison to experimental results.

implement the tight and loose coupling algorithms that the implicit and explicit nature of the two fluid solvers demands. A number of examples are shown demonstrating the use of the framework in calculating problems specified by the SLOWD verification and validation plan.

In the final stage of the SLOWD project, the framework will be applied to industrially-led sloshing problems and demonstrated in terms of its usefulness as part of an overall design workflow. Due to the commercial nature of the software created, direct availability of the framework is currently limited to the SLOWD project consortium, however a similar design and concept can be accessed via an open source framework created as a parallel activity within the same work package [25].

Further development will also take place to integrate a MATLAB Simulink controller model into the overall framework. Generally this will be achieved by instrumenting code generated automatically by MATLAB using the MUI library and then applying forcing to the structural model through communications passed via the ABI-Proxy application. The coupled fluid models will not be directly aware of the controller which will be coupled directly to MSC Nastran, however validation of the implemented FSI algorithms will be necessary in terms of how robust they are when the structural response behaves not only according to interactions with a fluid but also due to a forcing constraint introduced by the controller.

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